

An Analysis and Strategies to Enhance Students Interest and Participation in Informatics Learning on App Inventor Topic Utilizing Mobile Devices: A Case Study of Classroom Learning Sessions in Class of F6 at SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta

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Abstract:

This research aims to analyze and develop strategies that can enhance students' interest and participation in informatics learning on App Inventor subject using mobile devices, with a case study of classroom learning sessions in class of F6 at SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta. The research method used is a qualitative method. Data collection methods in this research include observation, distributing questionnaires to students, and teacher interview. Respondents in this study were a class of F6 students totaling 31 people, consisting of 10 female students and 21 male students. The limitation in this study is that only a small number of students bring laptops to informatics lesson. The results showed that the school's slow internet connection, lack of interest in bringing laptops, lack of skills in using laptops, and the availability of personal laptops were the main challenges to student participation in teaching and learning activities, especially in App Inventor subject. However, using certain strategies such as optimizing the use of mobile devices enables continuous learning inside and outside the classroom.

Keywords: *App Inventor, Informatics learning, SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta, Student participation*

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1. Introduction

Student interest and participation in the learning process are important elements that greatly affect the success of education. Student interest in a subject can enhance the enthusiasm of learning participation, whereas active participation in classroom activities facilitates a deeper comprehension of the subject matter being presented. Interest and participation, especially in informatics learning is very important because the informatics field involves a strong understanding of concepts and practical skills.

Informatics learning in schools is an important component in today's curriculum, given the importance of information and communication technology in the ever-evolving digital era. Informatics not only teaches technical skills, but also trains students to think logically, creatively and critically. Such skills are indispensable in various fields of work in the future. Therefore, ensuring that students are interested and actively participate in informatics learning is an important task for educators (Mashudi, 2021). Thus many countries have incorporated informatics into the education curriculum to ensure that students have the necessary knowledge and skills to succeed in the digital era.

One of the topics in the informatics subject is App Inventor. MIT App Inventor is a platform that allows users, including students, to create Android apps in an easy way. MIT App Inventor is becoming a valuable tool in education, helping to introduce the world of app development to the younger generation and supporting teaching and learning in an innovative and engaging way. App Inventor learning not only introduces students to the basic concepts of programming, but also gives them the opportunity to develop their creativity through creating apps that can be used in everyday life. Therefore, teaching this topic is very beneficial in improving students' technical skills and interest in informatics.

However, based on observations in situations that require in-class learning, challenges arise when most students do not have access to laptops or technological devices needed to understand the topic in depth outside the computer laboratory, which can certainly hinder mastery of the topic and reduce student participation in learning. This becomes more relevant in the context of learning App Inventor topic in class of F6 at SMAN 4 Surakarta, where students must develop skills in application programming without always relying on laptops. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze and develop strategies to enhance students' interest and participation in learning Informatics, especially App Inventor topic and ensure that students are capable of achieving effective learning outcomes even without the use of laptops.

2. Related Work

Previous research has extensively explored various strategies to enhance student interest and participation in informatics learning on App Inventor topics, particularly through the integration of mobile learning applications and innovative teaching tools.

2.1. Interests

Interest in learning plays a crucial role in determining student engagement and academic success. It has been shown that students who exhibit high levels of interest in their studies are more likely to be enthusiastic about learning, actively participate in classroom activities, and achieve better academic outcomes.

Amalia (2024) emphasizes that student interest significantly influences their engagement and understanding, particularly in challenging subjects like mathematics. Her study at SMK Negeri 1 Padaherang demonstrates that strategies aimed at boosting student interest can lead to higher levels of comprehension and retention of material. Amalia's research highlights the importance of creating engaging and relevant learning experiences to maintain and enhance student interest.

The role of interest in learning has been extensively studied, highlighting its critical impact on student engagement and academic success. Interest can drive students to engage more deeply with the subject matter, fostering a more profound understanding and retention of knowledge. A study by Vian (2024) emphasized the importance of fostering student interest to enhance learning outcomes, particularly in challenging subjects. Vian (2024) discusses the impact of learning interest on student participation and motivation. His research conducted in SMP Negeri Sekecamatan Parindu, Kabupaten Sanggau, found that students with a higher interest in physical education were more motivated and active in their participation. This study underscores the need for educational strategies that foster and sustain student interest to improve overall educational outcomes.

Additionally, a study by Salma *et al.* (2024) further noted the significance of interest in learning by examining motivational techniques and engaging teaching methods. Their research in SDIT Khairur Rahman shows that implementing these strategies can significantly enhance student interest, leading to better academic performance and a more enjoyable learning experience.

Interest plays a significant role in the learning process. The study by Zain *et al.* (2023) indicates that students with high learning interest are more motivated to learn, find it easier to comprehend the lesson material, and are more active in participating in the learning process. Zain *et al.* (2023) provide insights into the relationship between student interest and their motivation to learn. Their study indicates that students who are highly interested in their studies are more likely to engage deeply with the content, participate actively in classroom activities, and achieve better academic results. Zain *et al.* emphasize that fostering student interest should be a key focus in educational practices to enhance learning outcomes.

These studies collectively highlight the critical role of interest in learning. They suggest that enhancing student interest through engaging, relevant, and motivational strategies can significantly improve student participation, understanding, and academic performance.

2.2. Interests Theory by Hidi and Renninger

Interest theory proposed by Hidi and Renninger (2006) explains that interest develops through four phases: situational interest triggered, situational interest maintained, emerging individual interest, and well-developed individual interest. The theory emphasizes that interest is not just a fixed individual characteristic, but can be grown and developed through experience and interaction with the learning environment (Hidi and Renninger 2006).

In terms of informatics learning on App Inventor topics with mobile device-based, this theory is highly relevant. Many students have situational interests triggered by interesting tasks or activities in the classroom. However, in order to deepen and personalize students' interests further, teachers need to create a supportive learning atmosphere and provide a variety of meaningful and enjoyable experiences.

By utilizing alternative resources and creative teaching methods, teachers can help students develop a deeper interest in informatics, even without using laptops. For example, by using simulations, group discussions and projects, teachers can maintain students' interest and increase their engagement in learning.

2.3. Student Participation

Previous research by Anggulan and Suneki (2024) examined the effectiveness of presentation methods in increasing student engagement and learning outcomes in Pancasila education. Their research conducted in a high school setting revealed that interactive presentation techniques, which actively involve students in the learning process, significantly enhance their participation and motivation. By encouraging students to take part in presenting, the study found that learners were more engaged and actively involved in classroom activities.

Similarly, Wahyuni *et al.* (2022) explored the implementation of the Think-Pair-Share (TPS) model to boost student participation in elementary school settings. Their study demonstrated that the TPS model effectively promotes individual thinking, peer collaboration, and sharing of ideas within the class. This approach not only increased student participation but also enhanced their comprehension and retention of the subject matter, showcasing the benefits of collaborative learning.

A more recent study by Asep *et al.* (2023) provided a detailed examination of active learning strategies aimed at enhancing student participation. Their research highlighted the importance of creating dynamic and interactive classroom environments where students are encouraged to engage. Techniques such as group discussions, problem-based learning, and the use of multimedia resources were discussed as effective ways to engage students and foster an interactive learning atmosphere.

These studies collectively emphasize the importance of student participation in the educational process. They illustrate a variety of strategies and methods that can be utilized to create a more engaging and participative classroom environment, which in turn leads to improved academic outcomes and a richer learning experience for students.

2.4. Student Participation Theory oleh Newmann, Wehlage, dan Lamborn

The Student Participation Theory proposed by Newmann, Wehlage, and Lamborn in 1992 focuses on the factors that influence students' active participation in learning activities. According to the theory, student participation is influenced by the relevance of learning materials, a supportive learning environment, and positive relationships between teachers and students (Newmann *et al.*, 1992).

In the case study in class of F6 at SMAN 4 Surakarta, this theory helps to understand how teachers can enhance students participation in informatics learning without the use of laptops. Teachers can enhance students' participation by creating relevant and meaningful learning activities for students. In addition, by establishing positive and supportive relationships, teachers can create a learning atmosphere that encourages students to participate actively.

For example, the teacher can connect the App Inventor topic about Notifier in a simple calculator project with real situations that are relevant to students' daily lives. This step can make the topic feel more meaningful and useful, so that students are more motivated to actively participate even without using a laptop.

2.5. Informatics Learning

Informatics learning is a teaching and learning process that involves basic computer science concepts and their applications. Research by Grover et al. (2020) highlights the importance of integrating computational thinking into K-12 education. Their study emphasizes that computational thinking is crucial for developing students' problem-solving skills and understanding of computer science concepts. By operationalizing computational thinking within STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education, Grover and colleagues found that students were better equipped to tackle complex problems, demonstrating improved cognitive and practical skills. In today's digital era, skills in informatics are crucial and an integral part of the education curriculum in various countries.

2.6. App Inventor

Pratama, Anggoro, and Kurniawan (2021) studied the effectiveness of MIT App Inventor in teaching programming to high school students. They found that App Inventor not only helped students grasp fundamental programming skills but also stimulated their creativity and problem-solving abilities. This aligns with the goals of enhancing both interest and practical skills in informatics education. Previous research by Pratama, Anggoro, and Kurniawan (2021) explored the use of MIT App Inventor in developing educational applications. Their study found that students could easily grasp programming concepts through the intuitive drag-and-drop interface of App Inventor, which facilitated a deeper understanding of the underlying logic and structure of coding.

Similarly, a more recent study by Wang et al. (2021) investigated the impact of using MIT App Inventor on students' programming skills and attitudes towards learning programming. The results indicated significant improvements in students' problem-solving skills and a more positive attitude towards learning programming, attributing these outcomes to the hands-on, interactive nature of the tool.

Additionally, Lang and Tezel (2022) provided a comprehensive guide on how to utilize MIT App Inventor for educational purposes. Their work emphasizes the tool's potential in making programming more accessible to a broader audience, including younger students and those with no prior programming experience. They highlight various educational strategies and projects that can be implemented using App Inventor to foster creativity and innovation.

Another significant contribution to this field is by Edriati et al. (2021), who highlighted the benefits of using MIT App Inventor in the classroom. Their research found that the tool not only enhances students' creativity but also significantly boosts their interest in programming. By allowing students to design and develop their own applications, App Inventor makes the learning process more engaging and relevant to their daily lives.

Moreover, Salamah et al. (2020) emphasized the effectiveness of MIT App Inventor in teaching programming to high school students. Their findings suggest that the tool significantly improves both student engagement and understanding, as it allows students to visualize and interact with the programming concepts in a tangible way.

Finally, these studies collectively underscore the effectiveness of MIT App Inventor as a powerful educational tool. They highlight its ability to simplify the learning process, engage students in hands-on projects, and foster a positive attitude towards programming. By integrating MIT App Inventor into the curriculum, educators can enhance students' understanding of programming concepts and prepare them for more advanced studies in computer science.

Building on these studies, our research aims to develop and analyze strategies specifically tailored for enhancing student interest and participation in the topic of MIT App Inventor in-class learning session utilizing mobile devices. By focusing on a case study in Class F6 at SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta, this study contributes new insights into effective educational practices in environments with limited technological resources.

3. Methodology

Qualitative research is one of the research methods that aims to gain an understanding of reality through an inductive thinking process (Adlin *et al.*, 2022). Qualitative research methodologies encompass the utilization of data collection instruments such as interviews, observations, and questionnaires (Abduh *et al.*, 2023). This research uses

qualitative methods to collect relevant data regarding student interest and participation in informatics learning on App Inventor topic with a case study focus on learning in-class sessions without using a laptop at SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta. The form of data collection in this study is through observation of participants who have been selected through purposive sampling technique.

Data collection was done through three main techniques: observation, questionnaire, and teacher interview. The first technique was observation, which was conducted during the learning session to observe students' interaction with the material and how they participate in the class. The following are observations conducted during the learning session in the F6 classroom to observe students' interaction with the topic and how they participate in the class. Observations in the form of a checklist are presented in a table.

Table 1. Observation of Learning Sessions in the Classroom

Num.	Student Activity Observation
Section 1: Student Attendance	
1	Observation number of students.
2	Name or initials of observed students.
Section 2: Interaction with Material	
3	Check (Y/N) if the student is reading or listening to the taught material.
4	Check (Y/N) if the student is taking notes during the lesson.
5	Check (Y/N) if the student is not interacting with the material.
Section 3: Active Participation in Class	
6	Check (Y/N) if the student is asking questions.
7	Check (Y/N) if the student is answering questions.
8	Check (Y/N) if the student is actively participating in discussions.
9	Check (Y/N) if the student is not participating in the lesson.
Section 4: Notes	
10	Additional notes deemed necessary to explain the student's behavior or interaction during the learning session.

The second technique used a questionnaire. Questionnaires were distributed to students to collect data on their interests, experiences, and obstacles they face in learning informatics without the use of laptops. Researchers conducted a survey by distributing questionnaires as research instruments to students by considering students' experience in learning activities. In this study, the researcher chose one of the classes, namely class of F6 at SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta as the object of research. The class was chosen because the researcher had practiced teaching in the class based on the results of the assignment from the student teacher, as well as the participation of students in informatics subjects, which then became the selection criteria for the object of research. Respondents in this study totaled 31 people consisting of 10 female students and 21 male students. The following is a table of respondent data in this study, namely:

Table 2. Respondents

Gender	Total	Percentage
Female Students	10	67.74 %
Male Students	21	32.26 %
Total	31	100 %

The first form of data collection in this study is through observation of participants who have been selected through purposive sampling technique. Observation data obtained by conducting a survey by distributing observation questionnaire sheets in the form of google forms to F6 class students of SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta and interviews with F6 class Informatics teacher. Students are expected to fill out the questionnaire within a predetermined time frame. The questionnaire data that has been filled in by students will then be analyzed by researchers. The following is a research questionnaire given to students:

Table 3. Research Questionnaire

Num.	Question
Section 1: Technology (Laptop) Interest and Readiness	
1	Do you have a personal laptop?
2	Do you have regular access to a laptop at home?
3	How interested are you in learning informatics?
4	How prepared are you to use laptops for informatics learning in the classroom?
5	What do you like about using laptops in informatics learning in the classroom?
6	If there are other reasons, please write them down:
7	What do you dislike about using laptops in informatics learning in the classroom?
8	If there are other reasons, please write them down:
9	What do you think can be done to bring and increase the use of laptops in informatics learning in the classroom (when learning is not in the computer lab)?
Section 2: Technology (Laptop) Usage	
10	Do you bring your laptop to school every day
11	How often do you use your laptop for informatics learning in the classroom (not in the computer lab)?
12	What do you use the laptop for in informatics learning?
13	If there are other reasons, please write them down:
14	In your opinion, how important is the use of laptops in informatics class?
15	Do you feel comfortable using a laptop for classroom learning?
16	What are the obstacles you experience when using laptops in informatics learning?
17	If there are other reasons, please write them down:
Section 3: Strategies to Enhance Interest and Participation	
18	What do you think can be done to increase your interest in learning informatics without using a laptop?
19	If yes, what is the reason why you have attended Informatics lessons without a laptop?
20	If there are other reasons, please write them down:
21	What do you think about learning Informatics without a laptop?
22	What do you think are the benefits of learning Informatics without a laptop?
23	If there are other reasons, please write them down:
24	What do you think are the disadvantages of learning Informatics without a laptop?
25	If there are other reasons, please write them down:
Section 4: Strategies to Enhance Interest and Participation	
26	What do you think can be done to increase your interest in learning informatics without using a laptop?
27	Please provide an example:
28	What do you think can be done to increase your participation in informatics learning without using a laptop?
29	Please provide an example:

30	What do you expect from learning Informatics to be more interesting even if you don't bring a laptop?
31	What ways do you think can be used to increase student participation in learning Informatics without using laptops?
32	Please provide an example:
Section 5: App Inventor Topic	
33	Have you ever studied App Inventor?
34	Where are your resources for learning App Inventor materials?
35	If yes, what do you think about learning App Inventor without a laptop?
36	What are some ways you think you can learn App Inventor in class if you don't use a laptop?

Finally, the third data collection technique is conducting interviews. The interview with the teacher aims to get the teacher's views and strategies in enhancing student participation and overcoming technological limitations in the classroom. The following is a list of interview questions with Informatics teachers:

Table 4. List of Interview Questions with Informatics Teacher

Num.	Question
Section 1: Interest in Utilizing Technology	
1	How do you think students' interest in informatics learning is?
2	Do you see any difference in interest between students who have access to laptops and those who don't?
Section 2: Student Participation	
3	How is student participation in class when they are not using laptops compared to when they are using laptops?
4	Do you see a difference in understanding the material between students who use laptops and those who don't?
Section 3: Technology Availability and Usage	
5	What do you think is the main factor that causes most students not to bring their laptops to informatics lessons?
6	Do you observe any problems related to the use of laptops in informatics learning in class F6?
7	What are the most common obstacles you encounter related to students' use of laptops in class?
Section 4: Learning Strategies without The Use of Laptops	
8	What strategies have you tried to teach informatics using gadgets or without laptops?
9	What strategies have you implemented to overcome the limited access to technology in this learning?
10	How effective do you think the strategies you have implemented are?
11	What are the main challenges in teaching informatics without using a laptop?
Section 5: Teacher Facilitation of Learning	
12	How do you think teachers play a role in facilitating informatics learning without laptops?
13	Are there any special methods or techniques you use to keep students engaged and active during learning?
Section 6: Alternative Resources and Learning Topics	
14	What are some alternative resources you use in informatics learning without a laptop?

15	How do students respond to the use of these alternative resources?
Section 7: Support from the School	
16	How much support from the school in overcoming obstacles related to limited access to technology among students?
17	What are your suggestions for improving school support in this regard?
Section 8: Suggestions and Insights	
18	What are your suggestions to overcome the problem of limited laptops in informatics learning?
19	Do you have any suggestions or recommendations to improve student participation in informatics learning without using laptops?

4. Results and Discussion

The importance of teachers cannot be overstated in guiding students towards optimal learning. Teachers have the capacity to utilize fundamental principles from educational science in the discernment of suitable subject matter, design effective curriculum structures, and apply relevant teaching methods to meet students needs (Syafi'i, 2023). In addition, teachers are responsible for increasing student interest and participation in informatics learning through innovative approaches and creating an engaging learning environment. A competent teacher should possess the capacity to stimulate student engagement effectively, providing guidance, as well as support in achieving learning goals (Nurzannah, 2022). Teachers not only act as facilitators, but also as motivators who can enhance student involvement in the learning process. The right approach can help students understand the topic better and stimulate their interest in informatics learning, even without the direct use of laptops. Through effective and innovative strategies, teaching goals can be achieved with greater efficacy, and students can gain the skills and knowledge needed to face challenges in this modern age.

The following are the results and discussion of research on strategies to enhance student interest and participation in informatics learning on App Inventor topic utilizing mobile devices or without using laptops conducted by researchers, the results obtained through analysis of observation, questionnaire, and interview data using description analysis as follows:

4.1 Result

4.1.1 Observation Results

This section discusses the results of observations conducted during the learning session in class F6 at SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta. The purpose of these observations was to monitor student interactions with the learning material as well as their participation in class discussions. The data collected includes aspects of student attendance, interaction with the material, active participation in class, and additional notes regarding student behavior during the learning session. Below are the findings from the observations conducted.

Table 5. Results of the Classroom Learning Session Observations

Num.	Observation Aspects	Description of Findings	Percentage
1	Student Attendance	All 31 students were present during the learning session.	100%
2	Interaction with Material	16 students were actively reading or listening to the taught material.	51.61%
		5 students were taking notes during the lesson.	16.13%
		10 students did not interact with the material.	32.26%

3	Active Participation in Class	4 students asked questions.	12.90%
		5 students answered questions posed by the teacher.	16.13%
		13 students actively participated in the discussion	41.94%
		9 students did not actively participate in the discussion.	29.03%
4	Notes from 9 students who did not actively participate in the discussion	3 students appeared silent and showed no participation	-
		2 students appeared drowsy during the learning session.	-
		2 students were frequently chatting with their peers.	-
		2 students were seen playing on their phones while the teacher was instructing.	-

The observations in Table 5 indicate that despite the challenges of learning without laptops, students still demonstrated a considerable level of interest and participation in class. Out of the total 31 students observed during the learning session, all students were present in class. In terms of interaction with the material, 16 students (51.61%) were actively reading or listening to the taught material, while 5 students (16.13%) were seen taking notes during the lesson. However, 10 students (32.26%) did not interact with the material at all.

Students worked in small groups, with some students assisting their peers who had difficulty understanding the material. In terms of active participation in class, 4 students (12.90%) asked questions, and 5 students (16.13%) answered questions posed by the teacher. Additionally, 13 students (41.94%) actively participated in class discussions, demonstrating their engagement in the learning process. The remaining 9 students were more passive and awaited directions from the teacher, indicating that there are still students who are less involved in the learning process. Among the 9 students who did not actively participate in the discussion, 3 students were observed to be silent and showed no participation, 2 students appeared drowsy during the learning session, 2 students were frequently chatting with their peers, and 2 students were seen playing on their phones while the teacher was instructing.

Students showed initial interest in the App Inventor material, but most appeared confused without laptops. Some students felt frustrated and passive without laptops, leading to behaviors such as daydreaming, playing with gadgets, and socializing with friends. Nonetheless, they still attempted to understand the material through discussions. Overall, students appeared enthusiastic despite the technological limitations. The percentages from the observation results provide a general overview of the levels of participation and interaction with the material in class, which can serve as a basis for developing more effective teaching strategies.

4.1.2 Personal Laptop Ownership

In the F6 class of 31 students, there is a difference in the availability of personal laptop devices for informatics learning. Of the total students, 20 of them have access to personal laptops that can be used during learning. The availability of these devices can be an opportunity for teachers to enhance student engagement in learning, allowing them to be more involved in programming activities and the use of relevant software.

However, there are also 11 other students who do not have their own laptops and have to borrow during informatics lessons. This shows the differences in access that exist among students which can affect the level of engagement and participation in learning. Therefore, it is important for teachers to design learning strategies that take into account the needs and availability of student devices, so that all students can benefit from informatics learning without exception.

Table 6. Personal Laptop Ownership

Number of Students	Description	Percentage
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20 Students	Owning a Laptop	64.5
11 Students	Don't have a laptop	35.5

Laptops are essential in informatics learning in class as they are the main tool for access to various digital learning resources, such as online learning materials, tutorials, and programming resources. With laptops, students can do programming practice independently and develop their technical skills. Therefore, having access to laptops is key to maximizing informatics learning in the classroom and preparing students to master the field of information technology.

4.1.3 Readiness to Participate in Informatics Learning in the Classroom or outside the Computer Laboratory

Informatics learning is an important part of the education process in this digital era. However, the challenge arises when most students do not have access to laptops or technological devices needed to understand the App Inventor topic which consists of creating designs and compiling code blocks in depth outside the computer lab. Therefore, this research aims to explore strategies that can enhance students' interest and participation in learning informatics, especially App Inventor, without the use of laptops. One aspect that becomes the main focus of this research is students' readiness to participate in informatics learning in the classroom, where the use of laptops should be maximized.

The following are some of the reasons for students in class of F6 at SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta regarding their readiness to participate in informatics learning in the classroom:

Table 7. Students' Readiness to Participate in Informatics Learning in the Classroom

Num.	Reason	Percentage
1	Lack of readiness from conducting learning sessions within the classroom, as it is commonly held in the computer laboratory	41%
2	Don't have a laptop	29%
3	Not interested in bringing a laptop	19,4%
4	Not aware of the information that the computer lab is being used for other activities	19,4%
5	Laptop is malfunctioning	6,5%
6	Want to focus on concepts and theories	6,5%
7	Want to interact and play more with classmates	6,5%

From the results of the questionnaire distributed to students of class F6 of SMAN 4 Surakarta, it can be seen that most students (41%) do not feel ready to follow informatics learning in the classroom. The main reason expressed by the students is that the learning is commonly held in the computer laboratory. In addition, 29% of students did not have their own laptops, while 19.4% of students stated that they were not interested in bringing laptops to school. 19.4% of students also stated that they did not know the information that the computer laboratory was being used for other activities. Meanwhile, as many as 6.5% of students revealed that their laptops were experiencing damage. In addition, another 6.5% of students stated that they wanted to focus more on the concepts and theories of the learning materials, while the rest wanted to interact and play more with classmates.

The various student reasons presented in Table 4 indicate the need for adjustments in learning strategies, as well as the utilization of other resources in order to improve students' readiness to participate in informatics learning in the classroom without using laptops. Efforts to increase students' interest and participation in learning also need to be strengthened with more creative and interactive approaches, as well as paying attention to students' needs and preferences in the learning process.

4.1.4 Obstacles to the Use of Laptop during Informatics Learning in the Classroom

One of the obstacles often encountered in using laptops in lessons is technical problems, such as hardware or software damage, which can disrupt the smooth progression of learning. Some of the obstacles that are often experienced by F6 class students at SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta are as follows:

Table 8. Obstacles to the Use of Laptop in Informatics Learning Sessions in the Classroom

Num	Problem	Percentage
1	School internet connection is slow	71%
2	Not interested in bringing a laptop	29%
3	Less proficient in using a laptop	29%
4	Laptops are not available	25,8%
5	Students are bored because they already understand and are proficient	12,9%
6	No power outlets available	3,2%

Most students in class F6 faced problems accessing the internet due to the school's slow internet connection (71%). In addition, around 29% of students were not interested in bringing laptops, and the same number also experienced difficulties due to lack of proficiency in using laptops. Meanwhile, 25.8% of students do not have access to a laptop, which is the main tool in learning informatics in the classroom. This shows that there are challenges in utilizing technology, such as laptops and internet access. The availability of laptops has a very important role in informatics lessons because it is the main tool in carrying out various learning activities which include programming, exploring database concepts, and using various software. Through the utilization of laptops, students can directly apply the theories learned, conduct programming practices, and develop creative projects in a supportive environment. In addition, easy access to the internet and various digital resources allows students to keep abreast of the latest information technology developments. Thus, the availability of laptops not only facilitates more interactive and efficient learning, but also prepares students for real-world challenges in the growing information technology industry.

4.1.5 Advantages of Learning Informatics Using Mobile Devices

Although the use of laptops in informatics learning during in-class learning sessions is highly recommended, according to the questionnaire survey results there are some advantages that can be gained in situations where students do not have access to laptops. For example, learning without laptops can encourage creativity in finding alternative solutions, such as using other devices or doing practical activities that strengthen concept understanding. The following are the benefits that students feel when informatics learning is shifted to mobile devices:

Table 9. Advantages of Learning Informatics Using Mobile Devices

Num.	Advantages	Percentage
1	Less weight carried in the bag	61,3%
2	More focus on concepts and theories	41,9%
3	More social interaction and play with classmates	41,9%
4	Improve critical thinking and problem solving skills	35,5%
5	Improve communication and presentation skills	19,4%

Learning without the use of Laptop can help sharpen communication and collaboration skills between students, as students must work together to complete tasks using limited resources. Despite not using laptops in informatics learning, students can still experience some positives. About 61.3% of respondents felt that not carrying a laptop can reduce the burden they have to carry in their bags. In addition, 41.9% felt that they could focus more on the concepts and theories being taught. In addition, not using a laptop also provides an opportunity for more social interaction and play with classmates, as felt by 41.9% of respondents. Furthermore, around 35.5% of students considered that lessons without laptops in the classroom could improve critical thinking and problem solving skills. While 19.4% felt that it could also improve communication and presentation skills. While there will be many challenges, this experience can

also teach students about flexibility and adaptability in the face of change, skills that are invaluable in the ever-evolving world of information technology.

4.1.6 Interview with Teacher related to Problems in Learning Informatics on App Inventor Topic in the Classroom

According to the informatics teacher, students' interest in learning informatics in class F6 of SMAN 4 Surakarta reached 85%. This is due to the motivation and overview given by the teacher at the beginning of the lesson, so that students become enthusiastic about participating in the lesson.

However, learning informatics in-class sessions faced some challenges. One of the challenges is the small number of students who bring laptops to school, typically limited to one representative from each group. The main reason students do not bring laptops is the risk of accidents that could damage the laptop, such as being knocked over or sat on by another student. Despite this, there is no significant difference in terms of learning ability between students who bring laptops and those who do not. In addition to the laptop issue, another challenge faced was the lack of electrical plugs in the classroom. The lack of electrical plugs disrupted the informatics learning process, which lasted for 2x45 minutes, coupled with the school's slow internet connection.

Teachers' strategies in facing this challenge include mastering the topic well and providing motivation to students. When students do not bring laptops, teachers can give assignments using paper or books, which are then presented in front of the class. Other alternatives that can be used are Computer Lab 2, teaching modules, and reference sources such as library links, YouTube, and Google Scholar. Student response to the use of these alternative resources is positive. Students feel happy, not bored, interested, and enthusiastic. And a teacher can act as a companion for students who have difficulties. This role proved to be effective until students were able to teach their friends who did not understand the material. Another challenge is the slow speed of the school's WIFI which can use the LAN cable in Computer Lab 2. And if you have difficulty regarding electrical plugs, students can bring sockets and then use them together with other students.

The last strategy that a teacher can do is to use a cellphone instead of a laptop, which has a percentage of up to 60%. Mobile phones are considered more practical and have great potential in using App Inventor during classroom learning. Mobile phones owned by every student provide an advantage because they can be accessed at any time, so that informatics learning can take place without obstacles.

Table 10. Teacher's viewpoints and strategies

Viewpoints	Strategy
1. The small number of student who bring laptops when learning takes place in the classroom	Maximizing the use of Computer Lab 2, but when Computer Lab 2 is in use, the teacher strictly applies the rule so that each group representative brings a laptop.
2. Slow speed of the school's Wi-Fi signal	Using the LAN cable provided in Computer Lab 2
3. The limited availability of electrical outlets in the classroom	Students can bring a power outlet and use it together with others
4. Mobile devices actually have smaller screen dimensions than laptops and students may have difficulty adjusting..	Students can write their assignments on paper and then present them in front of the class by telling a story about the assignment they did. And the teacher also provides special links to provide references to help in doing student assignments.

4.2 Discussion

The results of the research on the analysis and strategies to enhance students' interest and participation in informatics learning on the App Inventor topic without using laptops in the classroom learning session show that there is a personal laptop ownership factor among students. Of the 31 students in class F6 SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta, it is known that there are 20 students who have laptops but on the contrary there are 11 students who do not have laptops. This will certainly cause obstacles during the teaching and learning process.

The role of the teacher in enhancing learning interest in informatics lessons is very important. As learning facilitators, teachers have the responsibility to create an environment that supports and stimulates students' interest in the subject matter. Teachers can create interesting and relevant learning experiences by integrating technology in learning, providing real-world case examples, and facilitating discussions that trigger critical thinking. In addition,

teachers can also act as mentors who provide support and guidance to students in exploring their interests and talents in informatics. With the right approach, teachers can help build a strong foundation for students' interest in informatics.

There are several strategies that can be used to enhance student interest and participation in informatics learning sessions in the classroom without a laptop on the App Inventor topic. When laptops are not available, instruction on the learning is by explaining the material and practicing in groups using smartphones led by the teacher in front of the class. Moreover, utilizing an LCD screen, teachers can access YouTube to provide supplementary explanations to students through tutorial videos. On the other hand, teachers can summarize the material in the form of PPT that is easily understood by students.

Once the strategy is implemented, it will provide several advantages in learning. These advantages are more social interaction and play with classmates, less weight carried in the bag, improved critical thinking and problem solving skills, improved communication and presentation skills, and finally more focus on concepts and theories. Here are some of the challenges that students often face when taking informatics lessons in class, along with strategies to overcome them:

Table 10. Challenges and Strategies of Informatics Learning in-Class Sessions

Challenge	Strategy
1. Students experienced boredom as the learning activities were conducted in the classroom rather than in the computer laboratory as usual.	1. Presenting challenges in the escalation of complexity of the calculator application to encourage students to be more active in learning.
2. Slow school internet connection	1. Schools can pursue the enhancement of Wi-Fi infrastructure within the premises to ensure that students can connect their learning devices to a fast and reliable network. 2. Schools can improve Wi-Fi speed to significantly enhance the learning experience for students.
3. A significant number of students arrive without laptops, despite the ongoing Informatics lesson that is still about adding complexity to calculator applications using MIT App Inventor which require practical implementation.	1. Preparing Kahoot! quizzes or other interactive online quiz applications or games related to App Inventor topic, which can be accessed via mobile phones. 2. Asking students who have prepared laptops to share with friends who do not bring laptops 3. Prepare other learning strategies and media so that the practical material can still be delivered to students who mostly do not bring laptops in class.
4. Less proficient in using a laptop	1. Teachers or schools can make special training for students who have not mastered laptops or applications used during informatics learning. 2. Optimizing peer tutors to assign advanced students to provide guidance to friends who are still developing
5. Students who already understand and are proficient tend to browse other things on their mobile devices, both social media and games.	1. Providing extra projects that are more challenging for students who already understand and are proficient to avoid boredom. 2. Optimize peer tutors to assign advanced students to mentor their developing peers to keep them focused and engaged in learning. 3. Make clear rules regarding the use of mobile devices during learning and provide consequences for students who violate them.
6. During the informatics learning session on App Inventor class, the paucity of students bringing laptops made it difficult to determine a strategy for continuing the practice of design and block editor in App Inventor material	1. Collaboration between students a. Dividing students into groups and ensure each group has at least two student with a laptop 2. Utilization of learning apps a. Utilizing learning applications that are interactive and in accordance with the taught material. For example, for learning using MIT App Inventor, students can use the MIT

	<p>App Inventor Companion application available on mobile phones to do hands-on labs in class.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Game-based learning <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Using a game-based learning application or platform that can be accessed via mobile phones. Game-based learning will make learning more interesting and interactive for students. 4. Utilization of E-learning platform <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Utilizing mobile-accessible e-learning platforms such as Google Classroom or Moodle. b. Teachers can upload materials, assignments, and quizzes to the platform so that students can access them anytime and anywhere through their mobile devices. 5. Utilization of online learning resources <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Directing students to use online learning resources such as learning videos on YouTube, khanacademy.org, or coursera.org that are relevant to the App Inventor material. b. Teachers can provide guidance or recommendations for good online learning resources to students. 6. Creating interactive tasks <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Giving assignments that can be completed through mobile devices such as making videos, or blogs about the App Inventor material projects that are being worked on. b. Students can use various apps available on their phones to create interesting and creative assignments.
7. No power outlets available	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The school installs or provides additional power sockets in the classroom. 2. Students bring power banks as an alternative to charging laptop batteries. 3. Manage the use of battery power more efficiently during the learning process.

5. Conclusion

This research aimed to analyze and develop strategies to enhance students' interest and participation in informatics learning on the App Inventor topic using mobile devices, with a case study of classroom learning sessions in Class F6 at SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta. The results indicated that technological limitations, such as the lack of laptops and slow internet connections, are the main challenges in increasing student participation. Nevertheless, strategies such as using mobile devices, project-based learning, and group discussions have proven effective in overcoming these obstacles. Students exhibited high interest and active participation when teaching methods were more interactive and relevant to their everyday lives.

Based on the results of the research analysis and strategies implemented to enhance student interest and participation in learning informatics on App Inventor topic utilizing mobile devices, it can be concluded that teachers have diverse perspectives regarding the challenges encountered during the teaching and learning process in informatics subjects. The primary challenge arises due to the prevalent inability of most students to bring laptops to informatics learning in-class sessions. In response, teachers have adopted a strategy utilizing App Inventor accessible by students via mobile devices such as smartphones. Consequently, mobile phones offer several advantages in informatics learning fostering students participation, enthusiasm, and sustained interest. Additionally, teachers play a pivotal role as mentors, providing support to students facing difficulties. This supportive role has proven effective, empowering some students to participate in peer tutoring or assist other students who are struggling with the topic.

5.1 Suggestions for Future Research

Future research should explore the use of alternative technologies beyond mobile devices, such as tablets or hybrid devices, to determine whether these tools are more effective in increasing students' interest and participation. Additionally, investigating how the physical learning environment, such as classroom layout and resource availability,

impacts students' interest and participation in informatics learning could be beneficial. Further longitudinal studies could monitor the long-term effects of using interactive teaching strategies to provide deeper insights into their effectiveness. Furthermore, diversifying teaching methods, such as flipped classroom or blended learning, could be explored and their effectiveness compared in enhancing students' interest and participation at various educational levels. By developing such research, it is hoped that new and more effective strategies can be identified to improve the quality of informatics learning, particularly on the App Inventor topic.

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